

CONCEPTUAL APPROACHES TO THE FORMATION OF A MODEL FOR THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURIST COMPLEXES

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Annotation. This article is a direct proportion of the change in the indicators of the number of tourists in the regions to the indicator of the relative attractiveness of the tourist complex, which in turn is the difference between the absolute value of the attractiveness of the tourist complex in question and the expected value of the attractiveness of the tourist complex, and the structural elements of.

Keywords. Sustainable Development, Tourist Complex, tourist infrastructure, development model, targeted programs.

The formation of a model of sustainable development of tourist complexes is currently an urgent problem due to the role of tourist complexes in the economy of the district, region and the country as a whole. As a basis for the development of a model for the sustainable development of tourist complexes, an integrated approach is proposed as a means of combining and systematizing factors affecting the management process and achieving goals. Combining the main components of the sustainable development of tourist complexes allows a systematic approach to the development and implementation of targeted programs and projects, without which it seems difficult to achieve the main goals of sustainable development.

Currently, sustainable development is being considered by scientists in two ways:

- as a subtype of the socio-economic system;
- as an independent type of territorial systems.

Systematization and analysis of the work of foreign and domestic scientists allowed us to propose an approach to understanding the sustainable development of tourist complexes as an independent type of territorial systems aimed at carrying out environmental and socio-economic activities in a particular area.

Types of stability of regional systems are characterized by signs, features of ecological, economic, social orientation and parameters of the business ability of Regions.

To characterize and determine the sustainable development of tourist complexes as an independent type of territorial systems, types, goals, principles, tools and destabilizing factors were identified (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structural elements of the sustainable development of tourist complexes as an independent type of regional systems¹

The basis for the sustainable development of tourist complexes is the availability of natural or socio-cultural resources in a particular area. Since the object of study of regional systems is unique tourist complexes that require the use and control of consumption of ecological, economic and social potentials, sustainable tourism must have an organized form and comply with certain models. Taking into account the possibility of applying the concept of stability of regional socio-economic systems and distributing its postulates to tourist complexes, it is also possible to talk about the parameters of achieving their stability, emphasizing unstable indicators that do not allow achieving balance in the development of territories according to the criteria of a stable state.

¹ Developed by the author.

By creating sustainability assessment models and making appropriate management decisions, the problems of sustainable tourism development can be solved in a complex way.

In terms of a systematic approach, any methods of scientific research are often based on the construction of mechanisms, models of various objects and subjects. In theory, it is the use of important models and, in a practical sense, the use of a specific functional, logical model that allows us to take corrective measures related to the rational use of the resource base of the territorial system. In addition, the logical model can include a certain set of economic, social, managerial, institutional, logistics, production and other parameters, as well as individual structural elements.

Any model can act as a kind of copy of real objects, therefore, the phrase "sustainable development model" should reflect the main features that are completely inherent in the modeling object itself, that is, the tourist complex.

The existing models of the development of sustainable tourism have emerged as an influence on the "endless growth of the tourism industry" and the impact of this growth on the development of tourist complexes, including environmental and social aspects. In 1985, the General Assembly of the World Tourism Organization prepared the document "tourism Charter and tourist code" and published the rule that residents of the tourist area should "ensure careful treatment of the natural and cultural environment with their attitude and behavior." At the same time, tourists visiting the resort should respect the traditions and culture of the local population. In 1995, the World Tourism Organization (WTO) adopted the document "agenda of the 21st century for tourism and tourism". The document emphasizes the importance of the impact of tourism on the economic development of the region, outlines the negative consequences of the development of the tourism sector (destruction of the culture of the host region, transport problems, dissatisfaction of local residents with tourists). The document states that the transition to a sustainable tourism development strategy will significantly improve the environmental and socio-economic situation in the regions where the tourism sector exists. To do this, it is necessary to replace the culture of intensive consumption with a culture of rational growth; to balance the economic and environmental factors of development; to find the common interests of tourists and local residents".

Analysis of the growth of the tourism industry through the construction of models-mainly of an optimization nature, was evaluated separately:

1. tourist resources,

2. demand for tourism,
3. development and placement of recreation areas,
4. formation of a system of tourist movements,
5. recreational service booking modeling

At the same time, all the listed methods and models are basically single-criterion models that do not take into account environmental and social factors.

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